

MRI-Grade Photoplethysmography Using Bundled Fiber Optics for Contactless Heart Rate Monitoring and Real-Time Gating

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Abstract

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) relies on physiological triggering for cardiac gating, typically using the R-peak of an electrocardiogram (ECG). However, ECG-based triggering faces limitations in MRI environments due to challenges in electrode placement, magnetic field interference, and RF-induced heating. Alternatively, contact photoplethysmography (PPG) offers a feasible solution; however, it suffers from reduced accuracy and requires the fixation of a probe on the finger tip. To overcome these limitations, this paper proposes an MRI-compatible system for contactless forehead PPG using bundled fiber-optic guides. The proposed approach eliminates electrical interference and ensures safety. A low-power sensor node is proposed to investigate the trade-offs among signal fidelity, energy efficiency, and system latency in on-device PPG. By combining programmable optical sources, an analog front-end, and BLE connectivity, the platform enables reproducible MRI experimentation. It fully processes the PPG data in just 2.8 ms onboard, utilizing a low-power ARM Cortex-M33 core running at 128 MHz. A feasibility study involving 8 subjects was conducted to evaluate the proposed system and demonstrate the effectiveness of the MRI-compatible contactless PPG using green/red light. Several fiducial points of the PPG waveform—foot, onset, and peak—were evaluated for trigger generation. Despite a physiological delay of ~100-150 ms relative to the R-peak of a reference ECG, the PPG-based R-peak point is reliably estimated with a jitter of 5.14 ms. The sensor node demonstrated the efficiency of the proposed solution operating with a 520 mAh battery for over 23 hours and integrates custom adapters for 2 m optical guides, ensuring safe electronic placement outside the MRI bore. These results confirm that our system can enable

prospective gating of MRI measurements without the practical challenges of securing ECG leads or a fingertip PPG. The proposed system paves the way for a safe, contactless, low-power, self-contained sensor node with onboard processing and an interference-free gating method, with the potential to redefine physiological monitoring workflows in MRI environments, enabling precise synchronization without electromagnetic interference.

CCS Concepts

• **Applied computing** → **Health care information systems**;
• **Hardware** → *PCB design and layout*; **Sensors and actuators**;
Digital signal processing; *Sensor devices and platforms*; *Wireless devices*.

Keywords

MRI-compatible sensors, PPG, cardiac gating, embedded electronics, biomedical signal processing, contactless monitoring.

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1 Introduction

A range of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) applications requires synchronization of data acquisition with the cardiac cycle (cardiac gating) [35, 38]. The standard method for cardiac gating is electrocardiography (ECG), which provides the heart's R-wave as a trigger signal [17]. Today's ECGs acquire multiple time-resolved signals from different leads, each representing a 1D voltage trace over time, allowing comprehensive monitoring of cardiac electrical activity [32]. However, using conventional ECG in the MRI environment poses significant challenges and safety risks [15, 16]. High-field MRI (3 T and above) amplifies interference and artifact issues in

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ECG signals [10]. In addition, operating electronics in these high fields is likewise very challenging [13, 24, 34]. While the static magnetic field distorts the ECG trace, notably through the magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) effect [17, 34], switching magnetic field gradients and radiofrequency (RF) pulses cause eddy currents in the body, leads, and electronics. Moreover, the MHD effect generates a voltage that changes the T-wave of the ECG. This can confuse gating algorithms, leading to mistimed or missed R-triggers at high field strengths. Additionally, RF-induced heating in the ECG leads is a serious safety concern—there are documented cases of patients suffering first- or second-degree burns from ECG electrodes during MRI scans [6, 21]. To mitigate these issues, MRI-compatible ECG systems utilize specialized non-ferromagnetic leads and careful routing; however, these measures do not entirely eliminate interference or risk [23, 24].

Derived from multi-lead ECG, vectorcardiography (VCG) reconstructs the 3D cardiac electrical vector and is employed in MRI for robust R-wave trigger detection at conventional clinical field strengths (1.5–3T) [24, 30]. It can effectively discriminate the R-wave vector from MHD and flow-induced artifact vectors, as they largely point in different directions in the three-dimensional space. However, at ultrahigh field strengths, the magnitude of MHD-induced voltages increases substantially, leading to pronounced distortion of the measured vector orientation, compromising the reliability of R-wave detection [14]. Despite its advantages, a VCG still requires multiple electrodes and shares ECG's susceptibility to RF interference and potential heating. Moreover, the setup is more complex, requiring precise electrode placement and a calibration phase, which increases preparation time. These limitations, particularly in high-field MRI, motivate the development of non-electrical, MRI-safe physiological monitoring methods.

Fiber-optic Photoplethysmography (PPG) has emerged as a promising solution for MRI-safe, reliable cardiac monitoring [20]. Traditionally, fiber-optic PPG has been implemented in a transmission mode at peripheral sites such as the finger. However, long pulse arrival time (PAT) at peripheral sites limits the accuracy of systolic triggering. Extending fiber-optic PPG to a reflective, contactless configuration on the forehead is particularly attractive, as it combines the short PAT of this site with the inherent advantages of fiber-optic systems. Moreover, fiber-optic sensors are inherently immune to electromagnetic interference. This completely avoids the safety hazards associated with electric leads and makes the approach fully MRI-compatible [17]. Using a contactless reflective PPG configuration further improves patient comfort and simplifies setup [17]. In a reflective PPG, the light source and photodiode can be housed together (or coupled to the same fiber bundle) and simply positioned near the skin (e.g., on the forehead) without the need for adhesive electrodes or tight contact pressure [28]. A fiber-optic PPG can thus provide artifact-free waveforms even in high-field MRI. Another advantage of optical PPG gating is the ability to use different light wavelengths to optimize signal quality. Conventional pulse oximeters use red (~660 nm) and infrared (~940 nm) light, which penetrate deeper into tissue and are ideal for measuring oxygen saturation [2]. However, at these wavelengths, the PPG signal is dominated by absorption in larger, deeper vessels and can be more prone to motion artifacts. In contrast, green light (~525 nm) penetrates only a few millimeters into the skin and is

strongly absorbed by the blood in superficial capillaries, yielding a high-amplitude pulsatile signal from the skin microvasculature. Research has shown that green-light PPG often has higher fidelity for heart rate detection during movement, due to its shallow sampling depth and reduced motion artifacts [27]. On the other hand, red-light PPG tends to have a better signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) as it probes larger blood vessels and delivers a stronger overall reflection signal. Thus, combining green and red wavelengths can be synergistic. The green channel provides robust timing information, while the red channel provides a high SNR reference. Using visible wavelengths (green 525 nm and red 625 nm) in a fiber-optic PPG system is also beneficial because standard fiber optics transmits visible light with low losses over several meters [18]. Moreover, human skin has been well-characterized at these wavelengths, and the combination of green and red allows the possibility of pulse oximetry (oxygenation measurement) in future implementations. Beyond oxygenation, the estimation of blood pressure could also be explored using a single wavelength [12].

This work introduces a fully optical MRI-compatible PPG gating system that enables cardiac triggering without the need for electrical leads. The operative concept is illustrated in Figure 1, where the central image shows the device in use during an MRI scan, the right side highlights the placement on the foreheads of four participants, and the left inset provides a detailed view of the hardware prototype. By leveraging dual-wavelength fiber-optic PPG and high-fidelity analog front-end timing, the system achieves cardiac phase detection even in the presence of MRI-induced electromagnetic interference. The proposed system not only eliminates electrical coupling, thereby mitigating risks of patient burns and shocks, but also improves gating accuracy in conditions where traditional ECG signals are distorted, such as at high magnetic field strengths (3 T, 7 T, and beyond). Beyond its safety implications, the contactless nature of the sensor simplifies the setup, potentially reducing patient preparation time, and improves patient comfort and safety during scans.

In more detail, this work introduces a pioneering contactless fiber-coupled PPG system for use within MRI scanners, featuring dual-wavelength visible-light sensing and a Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) wireless interface. To enable fiber-coupled, dual-wavelength PPG with low-power embedded processing, the proposed system is built around a multi-channel analog front-end designed for optical measurements [18], which allows for alternating green and red illumination and effectively captures two PPG signals simultaneously. The proposed design employs a sensor board (with its LED drivers and detectors) located outside the MRI bore, and fiber-optic bundles are used to deliver light to the subject and return the reflected signal. A dual-wavelength illumination scheme (525 nm and 625 nm) delivers and collects reflected light through a 2 m fiber bundle comprising dozens of 50 μm optical fibers. This configuration allows PPG acquisition at the forehead without metallic components, thereby eliminating electromagnetic coupling and heating risks. Because the fiber cable is non-metallic and non-conductive, it can be safely routed into the MRI bore and placed on the patient's forehead without concern of heating or image distortion. The sensor at the forehead consists of a small plastic optical probe that hovers just above the skin (with a few millimeters gap) in the temple or forehead area. The developed fiber-optic probe does not

Figure 1: Proposed device in operation inside an MRI scanner (Philips Healthcare). The central image shows a participant inside the MRI bore, with a fiber-optic cable running from the forehead to the developed board on the left. The sensor node is placed on a trolley and connected to the volunteer via a 2 m fiber-optic cable. The left inset provides a zoomed view of the prototype, highlighting the core components. On the right, four participants are shown wearing LEDs for PPG measurements. Figures A and C show the contactless setup with the green LED, and red LED in D. Figure B shows a contact setup using the red LED.

Table 1: Comparison of cardiac-gating methods in MRI reported in the literature. Delay and jitter are reported with respect to the ECG R-peak and are described in the respective references.

Reference	Method	Modality	Contactless	Delay [ms]	Jitter [ms]
[31]	Phonocardiography (PCG)	Acoustic	–	30	4.4
[22]	Seismography (SCG)	Mechanical	–	45-120	–
[11]	Ballistocardiography (BCG)	Mechanical	–	350-420	–
[26, 35]	Fiber Finger-PPG	Optical	–	348	35
[35]	Camera-PPG	Optical	✓	97	21.9
[29]	Doppler radar (CW radar)	Electromagnetic (Microwave)	✓	550	45
[37]	Pilot Tone (PT)	Electromagnetic (RF)	✓	179	9.4
[18]	Fiber Optic Sensor (FOS)	Optical	–	100-700	–
This Work	Fiber Forehead-PPG	Optical	✓	100	5.14

require adhesive; it can be held in place with a soft strap or lightly taped, making it effectively contactless for electrical connections. The battery-powered and optically isolated device introduces no measurable RF noise or artifacts in the images, validating the viability of fiber-optic PPG sensing for MRI-compatible physiological monitoring.

In pilot tests and during feasibility studies, the fiber-optic PPG achieved an excellent signal quality SNR inside a 1.5 T scanner—for instance, green-light PPG recorded in the MRI bore of about 22 dB. The proposed on-device algorithm tracks the cardiac cycle with high fidelity: using the PPG waveform’s foot as a fiducial point, the variation (jitter) in predicting the ECG R-wave timing is only ~5 ms. This timing precision is substantially better than reported for camera PPG gating (≥ 25 ms [4, 9, 33, 36]), used as a reference jitter for this work. Notably, the forehead PPG’s intrinsic delay (≈ 100 ms from the R-wave) is consistent, allowing it to be accounted for prospective gating.

2 Related Work

Numerous alternatives to ECG and VCG gating have been proposed, as summarized in Table 1. Nevertheless, none has yet demonstrated

a fully satisfactory solution. These methods can be broadly divided into contact-based and contactless approaches.

Contact-based methods, including phonocardiography (PCG) [31], seismocardiography (SCG) [22] and Doppler ultrasound (DUS) [19], have been explored for cardiac triggering in the MRI. PCG and DUS are highly susceptible to the intense acoustic noise generated by the scanner, whereas SCG and DUS are affected by patient motion and positioning. Furthermore, dependence on contact-based sensors and operator-dependent placement can hinder workflow efficiency and affect reproducibility in clinical settings. PPG has emerged as a promising surrogate measure of the cardiac cycle, as it is largely unaffected by distortions from the MRI environment [12]. Finger-PPG, implemented in transmission mode at the fingertip, is a contact-based technique that allows rapid setup, thereby improving workflow efficiency. However, the relatively long pulse arrival time (PAT) at this site (250 ms to 350 ms) delays the trigger until after systole [36]. Because diastole naturally varies in duration, the frames corresponding to the next systole may be assigned to different temporal bins, leading to temporal blurring in time-resolved measurements. The work [18] presents a comprehensive review

of fiber-optic sensor (FOS) systems for cardiorespiratory monitoring and triggering in MRI. The review identifies three principal open challenges that have prevented clinical adoption of FOS-based gating: (i) excessive signal delay relative to the ECG R-peak (approximately 200 ms for BCG-based FBG sensors, and up to 348 ms for peripheral finger PPG), which precludes prospective systolic triggering; (ii) the absence of contactless sensing configurations, with all reviewed systems requiring mechanical coupling to the chest, back, or abdomen; and (iii) the lack of self-contained, low-power acquisition hardware, as most systems rely on bulky external FBG interrogators with no quantified power autonomy. The system proposed in this work directly addresses all three challenges by repositioning the fiber-optic probe to the forehead in a contactless reflectance configuration.

Contactless methods aim to avoid direct patient touching, thereby reducing operator-dependent placement, infection transmission, and improving clinical workflow efficiency, while maintaining accurate cardiac detection. Contactless camera-based PPG (also known as remote or imaging PPG) uses a video camera to detect subtle changes in skin reflectance as blood pulses travel through peripheral microvasculature [33, 36]. It has been explored for MRI gating by monitoring areas such as the forehead, which is typically unobstructed by the MRI receive coils and provides a shorter PAT (90 ms to 100 ms) compared to peripheral sites [36]. This shorter PAT enables triggering before peak systole, allowing for the capture of systolic frames without the temporal blurring associated with long PATs, a critical consideration in applications such as flow MRI, where peak velocities serve as an important clinical marker of aortic stenosis [25]. However, despite this advantage, the trigger jitter (PAT variability) of 25 ms to 35 ms remains on the order of the MRI temporal resolution, which can still result in temporal blurring of the reconstructed frames. Currently, no PPG-based technique has been demonstrated to provide both a short PAT (<100 ms) and low jitter (<10 ms) sufficient for fully accurate systolic triggering. Pilot tone [37] uses an external RF transmitter to produce a continuous signal within the oversampled MRI receiver bandwidth, from which cardiac and respiratory motion can be derived. However, it exhibits higher latency and greater jitter than camera-based PPG. Finally, continuous-wave Doppler radar [29] detects chest wall motion via microwave reflections, providing a promising non-contact alternative. However, it requires careful in-bore placement to avoid MR interference and typically shows long pulse arrival times and increased jitter.

3 System Overview

The proposed system, shown in operation in Figure 1, comprises a custom fiber-coupled sensor node paired with onboard digital signal processing, a contactless optical human interface, and a receiver station for logging and further processing. Unlike conventional MRI gating systems that rely on wired ECG leads, our design achieves fully optical cardiac monitoring and trigger generation using dual-wavelength PPG. The system integrates seamlessly with existing MRI hardware through a TTL-compatible synchronization output and BLE, enabling precise cardiac gating without introducing electromagnetic interference. This architecture establishes a

safe, MRI-compatible, and electrically isolated pathway for reliable cardiac signal acquisition and control.

3.1 Sensor Node Hardware Design

A custom, battery-powered, low-power sensor node has been developed to operate in the MRI. It integrates the hardware required to acquire PPG signals using the fiber optic bundle described in Section 3.2. The hardware design, introduced in Figure 1 and detailed in Figure 2, is based on two main components: an nRF5340 MCU for onboard computation and wireless connectivity, and the ADPD4100. The latter is a complete multimodal sensor front end, stimulating up to eight light-emitting diodes (LEDs) and measuring the return signal on up to eight separate current inputs, e.g., photo-diodes. The board also includes the necessary interface to the optical adapter, enabling efficient light coupling into the fibers. In addition to its core function, the PCB incorporates additional features, including USB-based battery charging, battery monitoring, and optional data access via USB or SD card. Figure 2 illustrates the assembled prototype within its enclosure, showing how the optical adapter is partly integrated on the board and extends into the front wall, which can be slid into place.

The ADPD4100 is an all-in-one solution for multimodal optical sensing, which can drive 8 parallel channels with internal analogical conditioning and digital conversion. The IC includes on-chip digital filtering and supports SPI communication and four GPIOs. In our design, two of the eight LED channels are utilized to leverage the properties of the red and green wavelengths described in Section 3.3, and two input channels are connected to photodiodes. Due to the critical alignment between the optical cable and the photodiodes, the two LEDs are located on a separate small PCB (Photodiode PCB) that is connected to the main PCB (PPG Measurement PCB) via wires. This allows the photodiodes to be placed at a 90° angle, pointing toward the front wall (part of the optical adapter) of the enclosure. The ADPD4100 is connected via SPI to the main MCU, the low-power system-on-chip (SoC) nRF5340 from Nordic Semiconductor. It features a programmable application core with a variety of peripherals, such as SPI or USB, along with a network core that includes a BLE transceiver. It is located on the NORA-B106-00B module from u-blox, as highlighted in Figure 2. We selected this SoC due to its intrinsic robustness against electromagnetic noise and power supply fluctuations, and the presence of an onboard BLE transceiver. By avoiding external high-speed components and copper traces that capture magnetic noise, this SoC provides the perfect balance between computational performance and resilience against MRI interference. As a parallel feature, the sensor node can generate a TTL digital trigger to synchronize the MRI machine with the PPG signal. To this end, the sensor node integrates a small SMA coaxial connector.

The sensor node is embedded in a blue, semi-transparent enclosure, as shown in Figure 2. A small removable part in the compartment allows access to the battery without opening the entire enclosure. Furthermore, it features a removable front wall, which allows for easy replacement by a custom non-transparent 3D printed part (see Figure 2 in grey) that serves as an optical adapter, coupling the fiber optic bundles with the photodiodes and LEDs, and, at the

same time, decreasing the external noise coming from environmental illumination.

The entire board is powered by a single-cell 520 mA h lithium-ion battery, with a nominal voltage of 3.70 V. The LEDs are pulsed with 66 mA, as described in Section 3.3, and are powered by a dedicated 3.6 V buck converter with low quiescent current. Moreover, to interrupt the circuit in the event of an unexpected high current, resettable fuses have been installed on the power inputs, namely the USB 5 V connector and the battery connector. In the MRI environment, since time-varying (electro)magnetic fields induce voltage into conductors, the circuit can be exposed to higher voltages and ESD, which can cause components to operate unreliably or become damaged. To prevent this, ESD protection has been added at the USB connector, SD card slot, battery connector, and SMA connector. Power line protection consists of a TVS diode and an ESD-rated capacitor in parallel, whereas USB and SD signal lines feature a dedicated IC specifically designed for USB or SPI.

To provide a practical estimate of prototype cost, we include an approximate itemized breakdown of the main hardware components: integrated circuits (\$75), PCB fabrication and assembly in low volume (\$100), enclosure (\$5), fiber-optic components in low volume (\$2000), and battery (\$10). These values reflect prototype-scale implementation costs and are expected to decrease as production volume increases.

3.2 Fiber Optic Bundle

The optical interface between the sensing unit and the subject is implemented through a custom-made bundled fiber optic cable, fabricated by Fiberoptic-Heim (Bühler, Switzerland)¹ and depicted in Figure 3. The routing of the fiber-optic cable from the sensor node to the participant's forehead inside the scanner bore is illustrated in the central image of Figure 1. The fiber light guide is specifically built for operation in MRI environments. The assembly consists of two separate fiber bundles encapsulated within non-conductive flexible tubing. All structural elements, including silicone sheathing, polyether ether ketone (PEEK) ferrules, and anodized aluminum connectors, are completely non-ferromagnetic, ensuring full MRI compatibility. No metallic reinforcement or shielding is present, thereby preventing magnetic attraction, eddy current induction, or RF coupling in the scanner bore. Each individual fiber has a core diameter of 50 μm , with a mixed fiber arrangement for optimized coupling efficiency between illumination paths. A mixed-fiber layout is selected to minimize modal dispersion and coupling loss between the emitter and detector pathways. The connectors at both ends are mechanically keyed to ensure repeatable alignment and easy replacement. The cable ends are terminated in smooth, medical-grade optical tips that can be positioned in a non-contact regime at a few millimeters from the skin surface. The manufacturer reports attenuation values of approximately 0.2 dB m^{-1} at 525 nm (green channel) and 0.15 dB m^{-1} at 625 nm (red channel). The total fiber length employed in this work is 2 m, selected to allow a sufficient safety margin for routing the cables outside the high-field and gradient regions of the MR system while maintaining adequate optical throughput. In the implemented prototype, two distinct fiber bundles are integrated into the optical subsystem, as

¹<https://fiberheim.ch>

Figure 2: The top images show the assembled PCB within both the open and closed plastic enclosures. They illustrate how the PCB is mounted on the front wall and show the fiber-optic bundle (Section 3.2) connected to the analog interface. At the bottom, the figure displays the final design of the PPG Measurement PCB, with components marked and grouped using colored boxes.

shown in Figure 3: (i) Illumination bundle: transmits light from the ADPD4100 LED drivers (green and red sources) to the subject's forehead. The two input fiber bundles are merged after 45 mm into a single 6 mm cable, 2.2 mm and 3 mm for red and green LEDs, respectively. (ii) Detection bundle: returns the reflected light to the photodiode integrated in the ADPD4100 front-end. The 5.3 mm diameter on the photodiode side is studied to cover its whole active area.

The non-ferromagnetic construction and dielectric materials render the bundle intrinsically immune to RF-induced heating and magnetic field distortion. No measurable image artefacts or SNR degradation were observed during in-bore operation. The 2 m separation allows the active electronics and power supply to remain entirely outside the magnet room, protecting sensitive analog circuits from gradient noise and ensuring electrical isolation.

3.3 ADPD4100 Settings

The ADPD4100 is a multimodal analog front-end (AFE) chip developed by Analog Devices, specifically designed for optical sensing applications such as PPG. The 12 uniquely configurable time slots

Figure 3: Mechanical drawing of the custom MRI-compatible fiber-optic light guide (manufactured by Fiberoptic-Heim). The design employs mixed fibers (core diameter 50 μm) in non-ferromagnetic tubing/terminations (silicone, polyether ether ketone (PEEK), anodized aluminium) and chromed brass with a total length of 2 m for safe routing outside high-field gradient and RF regions of the MRI system.

allow simultaneous multi-wavelength measurements with an ambient light rejection of 60 dB up to 1 kHz. The ADPD4100, with its suitability for high-noise environments and low-power operation, makes it an ideal choice for applications such as portable diagnostic systems. For this reason, it has been selected as the central component for PPG signal acquisition in this study.

The ADPD4100 can be configured to operate in different modes. One of these modes is called *float mode*, which is specifically designed to increase the noise endurance of optical sensing. This operating mode relies on preconditioning the photodiode to a programmable bias before any pulse sequence. This effectively isolates the sensor from any DC bias and residual charge that might be accumulated. During the sequence, the photodiode is further modulated between a floating and connected state to the preceding transimpedance amplifier (TIA) stage. During the floating time, a photo-charge is accumulated at the photodiode junction, which is then transferred to the TIA/Integrator stage after connection. In combination with the ability to precisely control the LED drivers, we can construct the synchronous float sequence. The designed sequence utilizes the so-called *masked pulses*, during which the LED driver is off. Using an even number of pulses, the ADPD4100 is configured to subtract *masked pulses* from actual LED pulses (see Table 2). The purpose of this operational mode is to reject ambient light interference, offsets, and amplifier drifts. Moreover, the ADPD4100 internally employs a chopped integration sequence, by switching the integrator polarity in each pulse, reducing DC offsets, flicker noise ($1/f$), and charge injection. To optimise between a high sampling rate and SNR, a sequence with 4 pulses is chosen ($2 + 2$ *masked*). The resulting sequence for computing a single sample is shown in Figure 4. Using an optimised grid search, the remaining sequence parameters are selected based on SNR and the skewness signal quality index (S_{SQI}). These parameters can be found in Table 3.

Table 2: Description of the subtracting scheme of the ADPD4100 running a synchronous float sequence, where the mathematical operator subtracts ambient (amb.) and off-set (off.) noise from the signal (sig.).

Pulse	LED	Content	Operator	Purpose
1	OFF	amb. + off.	-	cancel noise
2	ON	LED + amb. + off.	+	sig. + noise
3	ON	LED + amb. + off.	+	sig. + noise
4	OFF	amb. + off.	-	cancel noise

Figure 4: Four-pulse synchronous float sequence for the acquisition of a single sample on the ADPD4100.

Table 3: ADPD4100 configuration and description linked to the sequence in Figure 4.

Parameter	Register	Hex	Value
LED Offset	0x0129 [7:0]	0x08	8 μs
LED Width	0x0129 [15:8]	0x05	5 μs
LED Driver Current	0x0125	0x002C	66 mA
Integrator Offset	0x012B	0x0140	10 μs
Integrator Width	0x012A	0x0003	3 μs
Minimum Period	0x0128	0x100B	11 μs
Chop / Subtraction	0x012D	0x9090	4-pulse
TIA Gain	0x0124	0x2200	200 k Ω

4 Embedded Processing Framework

This section details the onboard processing specifically designed for the proposed sensor node, introduced in Section 3.1. In addition to sensor and wireless drivers, the onboard software stack integrates complete data processing, including filtering and PPG detection. With this approach, we target low-power consumption and low-latency real-time gating, thereby removing the uncertainty of wireless transmission delay and the potential for remote computation (on a local server) to increase delay variability.

4.1 Sensor Node Onboard Processing

The embedded firmware of the PPG sensor node is developed using the Zephyr RTOS. It runs on a Nordic Semiconductor nRF5340 dual-core SoC, which integrates a Cortex-M33 application processor and a dedicated network processor for BLE operations. The firmware architecture is designed to enable real-time optical data acquisition, local digital signal processing, and wireless data transmission to an external receiver for logging and visualization.

The nRF5340 acts as a BLE peripheral device, advertising a custom GATT service for PPG streaming. The service implements multiple characteristics for optical waveform data, fuel gauge telemetry, and timestamp synchronization. The firmware is organized into three main layers: data acquisition, digital signal processing (DSP), and communication. The acquisition layer interfaces with the Analog Devices ADPD4100 optical front-end via the Zephyr device driver interface, sampling red and green LED channels in synchronized timing windows at 500 Hz. The windows include 50 samples with a period of 100 ms. Oversampling the PPG raw signal enables advanced digital filtering and precise jitter calculation; indeed, the DSP module performs in-node signal conditioning and feature extraction, including bandpass filtering and peak detection to identify cardiac cycles. The bandpass filter is a 6th order Chebyshev Type II in the 0.5 Hz to 6 Hz range, vectorized onboard the MCU with the *arm_biquad* in *float32*. In memory, we keep 10 s of previous data and between 5 peaks to 25 peaks detected in the past. The DSP framework is specifically optimized to reduce execution time and, consequently, decrease the power consumption. Each acquisition frame is preprocessed in real time onboard. This function performs filtering, normalization, and temporal peak prediction based on adaptive thresholds. The peak detection and prediction function relies on temporal continuity, as shown in Figure 5, predicting the next peak based on the previous 10 s history. To speed up execution, the data is sub-sampled by a factor of 10× for coarse peak detection and then processed entirely for fine peak detection around the coarse point. The optimized algorithm requires a total of 450 kB of RAM, and runs the complete pipeline in 2.8 ms, where 1.3 ms is required for data acquisition and filtering. When a new pulse peak or valley is detected, a structure containing the predicted timestamp is transmitted via a dedicated BLE GATT characteristic to the receiver node, enabling prospective systolic peak detection to trigger the MRI scan just on time. Moreover, the same prospective trigger is output via the TTL signal for local triggering via a wired connection. The complete data acquisition and processing requires 2.8 ms, only 3% of the available 100 ms intra-block period, allowing for future enhanced processing algorithms.

4.2 Data Logger and BLE Receiver

On the host side, a laptop or workstation functions as a BLE central node using a USB BLE adapter. A Python-based logger subscribes to GATT notifications and records all incoming data, including timestamps, for offline analysis and visualization. This setup enables live monitoring of optical signals while maintaining complete MRI safety, as the PPG node operates on battery power and communicates wirelessly.

Figure 5: Overview of the acquired data. The PPG signal is filtered and processed onboard, as in Section 4.1 and transmitted via BLE to the Data logger (Section 4.2). The plot shows the comparison between the real Peak and the Predicted Peak. The algorithm takes 5 heart rate periods to converge.

5 System Characterization

The sensor node was extensively tested both in controlled laboratory conditions and during MRI scans to decouple potential noise contributions from the MRI environment. These tests demonstrated that the device maintained a strong and reliable BLE connection, with negligible data loss or connection issues when the data logger was placed within a 10 m range. Figure 5 shows a sample of the acquired PPG signal, where filtering and peak detection are processed onboard the sensor node as described in Section 4.1. The peak prospective prediction takes 5 heart rate cycles to converge (R-R interval in Figure 7), predicting the next peak PAT_p based on the last detected PAT_f , named as Foot in Figure 5. The red cross is therefore used to prospectively trigger the next MRI scan via the wired TTL signal. Analysing the time precision and variability of such a prediction is essential for modelling the system's performance. We conducted a test under controlled conditions (constant illumination, static person, laboratory environment) to verify the accuracy of the PAT_p prediction against the actual (retrospectively determined) PAT_p , used as the ground truth. The result, depicted in Figure 9, shows how the error distribution follows a Gaussian curve, with an average around 0.6 ms and a standard deviation of 13 ms. Despite not being perfect, these values are sufficient to prospectively trigger an MRI scan, being less than 25 ms [4, 9, 33, 36].

5.1 PPG Measurement Analysis in Controlled Conditions

A pilot study was conducted to assess the feasibility of accurate prospective triggering using our optical fiber reflective PPG device on the forehead. The study aimed to achieve low latency (<100 ms) and low jitter (<10 ms) in an environment free from MRI-related noise. Eight subjects (1:1 gender ratio) participated in the study, with an average age of 25 ± 4 years and an average height of 172.0 ± 8.6 cm.

For this feasibility evaluation, an ECG system (Biocare ECG-2000) was employed to provide the R-peak reference trigger for cardiac gating. Four measurement conditions were tested with our sensor node, combining two illumination wavelengths—green (525 nm) and red (625 nm)—with both contact and contactless regimes. The

Figure 6: (a) PPG measurement in contact regime, (b) PPG measurement in contactless regime.

Figure 7: (a) PAT based on different fiducial points from the PPG waveform, (b) Acceptance regions for each fiducial point on the PPG waveform.

use of red and green light enabled the assessment of different optical penetration characteristics, as red light reaches deeper layers such as the hypodermis and pulsatile arterioles, while green light probes more superficial vascular beds. The contact configuration, serving as the baseline, ensured stable skin coupling through a custom PETG interface. In contrast, the contactless configuration, implemented at a distance of 1.5 cm to 2 cm using a similarly designed PETG attachment, was investigated as a promising approach for clinical applications, providing a fully contactless sensing alternative.

The PAT was calculated as the temporal interval between the R-peaks detected in the reference ECG signal and specific fiducial points in the PPG waveform, illustrated in Figure 7(a): the Pulse Arrival Time Foot (PAT_f), Pulse Arrival Time Onset (PAT_O), and Pulse Arrival Time Peak (PAT_p). The analysis aimed to quantify both the mean latency, representing the average temporal offset between the ECG and PPG signals, and the jitter, defined as the cycle-to-cycle standard deviation of latency measurements. Additionally, the heart rate (HR) and heart rate variability (HRV) were derived for each subject using the ECG R-peaks as reference triggers. To ensure the robustness of the analysis, only PAT measurements with fiducial points located within a defined temporal acceptance region were included (Figure 7(b)); detections outside this region were excluded. The corresponding acceptance rates are summarized in Table 5 and Table 7, providing a quantitative assessment of the reliability of fiducial point detection.

5.1.1 Red Light (625 nm) in Contact Regime. Table 4 reports the mean latency and corresponding jitter for each subject, calculated

Figure 8: Comparison of raw PPG data acquired through contact and contactless regimes at 525 nm (green) and 625 nm (red).

Table 4: PAT (mean) with jitter (std) for each subject in contact regime via red PPG with $f_s = 95$ Hz and 235 Hz. All values are in milliseconds.

Subject	PAT_f	$Jitter_f$	PAT_O	$Jitter_O$	PAT_p	$Jitter_p$
$f_s = 95$ Hz						
1	94.89	9.88	221.55	9.74	516.29	15.47
2	88.06	13.83	146.15	13.23	414.25	47.08
3	79.27	10.93	202.80	11.58	337.03	10.30
4	78.58	13.81	219.91	13.58	470.19	71.51
5	88.55	15.31	229.89	12.56	387.31	13.58
6	84.94	12.33	206.14	11.68	406.60	69.62
7	101.73	14.38	228.36	12.85	446.98	41.64
8	89.67	15.63	161.87	16.09	351.47	18.27
$f_s = 235$ Hz						
2	90.25	8.03	210.01	9.10	640.00	14.24
Mean	88.21	13.26	202.08	12.66	416.27	35.93

from 100 cardiac cycles per subject. Table 5 summarizes the mean peak detection rates and their standard deviations. Across all subjects, the average jitters for the three fiducial points are 13.26 ms, 12.66 ms, and 35.93 ms, respectively. Latency varies considerably with subject demographics, primarily age and blood pressure [1]. Subjects 1 and 8 exhibited the lowest and highest jitter, under 10 ms and over 15 ms, respectively. Notably, $Jitter_p$ (last column of Table 4) is markedly higher, averaging 36 ms and reaching up to 70 ms in subject 6, indicating substantial variability in peak detection.

The high variability of the systolic peak fiducial point is attributed to its inconsistent detection. As reported in Table 5, the mean peak detection rate is 72% with a standard deviation of 12.6%, and a substantial number of detected peaks fall outside the defined acceptance region, rendering this point an unreliable marker. In contrast,

Table 5: Detection rates (DR) for fiducial points within the acceptance region for red PPG in contact regime with $f_S = 95$ Hz and 235 Hz. All values in %.

Subject	Foot DR	Onset DR	Peak DR
$f_S = 95$ Hz			
1	100.0	100.0	72.2
2	100.0	89.7	64.8
3	100.0	100.0	94.7
4	98.8	100.0	63.9
5	100.0	98.5	59.7
6	100.0	100.0	75.0
7	100.0	98.9	67.4
8	98.9	95.6	52.2
$f_S = 235$ Hz			
2	100.0	100.0	69.8
Mean \pm Std	99.4 \pm 0.5	99.0 \pm 3.6	72.9 \pm 12.6

the foot fiducial point demonstrates the highest detection reliability, with a mean detection rate of 99.4% and a standard deviation of only 0.4%.

The acquisitions in Table 4 are sampled at 95 Hz and 235 Hz. The rationale is to compare different ADPD4100 settings in terms of jitter and peak detection accuracy. The jitter of PAT_f decreased by 42%, while the jitter of PAT_O decreased by 31%, down to 9.1 ms, which is expected since the sampling resolution is increased by 60%. A significant decrease in the jitter based on the systolic peak point can also be observed down to 14.2 ms, as compared to 47.1 ms in the previous measurement. Nonetheless, the peak detection rate remained significantly low with 30% of the detected points not falling within the acceptance region (see Table 5). The large difference in the PAT_p can be attributed to a large difference in the HR of the subject during both measurements from 66 bpm to 50 bpm. Although this sample is insufficient to generalize the percentage decrease of the jitter for the entire sample population, it can serve as a good approximation for a reasonable comparison between the two regimes.

5.1.2 Green Light (525 nm) in contactless Regime. In the contactless configuration, the measured jitters were 5.14 ms, 5.13 ms, and 19.76 ms for PAT_f , PAT_O , and PAT_p , respectively, using green light (525 nm) (see Table 6), representing a marked improvement over the contact regime. Pulse arrival times were generally consistent across subjects, with subject 8 exhibiting the lowest foot and onset jitters of 3.82 ms and 3.23 ms, whereas subject 7 showed the highest jitters of 8.78 ms and 6.61 ms. Notably, $Jitter_p$ remained substantially higher at 19.76 ms, indicating that the systolic peak remains unsuitable as a reliable trigger point.

Both the foot and onset points perform above expectations in terms of detection rate, with 100% and 99.88%, respectively. The 75.89% based on the systolic peak point is still significantly low, also considering the large jitter. The possible reasons for the improper detection of this specific point are further discussed in the next section.

Table 6: PAT (mean) with jitter (std) for each subject in contactless regime via green PPG with $f_S = 235$ Hz. All values are in milliseconds.

Subject	PAT_f	$Jitter_f$	PAT_O	$Jitter_O$	PAT_p	$Jitter_p$
1	107.70	5.25	178.85	4.92	391.91	30.48
2	85.18	4.76	159.90	5.48	335.13	10.20
3	89.54	3.72	175.67	6.00	332.16	8.01
4	108.37	5.60	184.58	5.36	416.87	39.26
5	90.82	4.62	187.48	4.27	310.76	6.64
6	108.99	4.54	186.82	5.14	367.54	22.16
7	108.23	8.78	210.51	6.61	388.04	13.17
8	97.15	3.82	170.84	3.23	415.11	28.18
Mean	99.50	5.14	181.83	5.13	369.69	19.76

Table 7: Detection rates (DR) for fiducial points within the acceptance region for green PPG in contactless regime. All values are in %.

Subject	Foot DR	Onset DR	Peak DR
1	100.00	100.00	59.26
2	100.00	100.00	100.00
3	100.00	99.00	91.00
4	100.00	100.00	63.53
5	100.00	100.00	98.61
6	100.00	100.00	71.08
7	100.00	100.00	24.72
8	100.00	100.00	98.85
Mean \pm Std	100.0 \pm 0.0	99.9 \pm 0.4	75.9 \pm 25.9

5.1.3 Suboptimal Regimes. Both the green contact and red contactless regimes were evaluated but found suboptimal due to limited signal quality and excessive noise, which prevented reliable PPG measurements in these configurations. In the green-contact configuration, the limited penetration depth of 525 nm light, combined with the minimum emitter-detector spacing imposed by the fiber-optic probe geometry (~ 8 mm), resulted in a very weak reflected signal without clear pulsatile features. In the red contactless configuration, the expected cardiac-frequency component was obscured by dominant low-frequency artifacts, likely due to ambient-light sensitivity, baseline fluctuations, and possible partial sensor saturation. In the contact configuration, green light (525 nm) is strongly attenuated within approximately 2 mm [3], and given the minimum emitter-detector separation of 8 mm in the fiber-optic probes, the signal reaching the photodetector is very weak. In the red contactless configuration (625 nm), although the fundamental cardiac frequencies are present due to deeper penetration (up to 5 mm), the signal is dominated by low-frequency noise caused by macroscopic tissue and skin movements. For these reasons, both regimes are unsuitable for fiber-optic PPG measurements in the MRI, supporting the hypothesis from the previous paragraph that optimal performance is achieved using green light in the contactless configuration.

5.1.4 Discussion. Overall, the pilot study results indicate that the contactless regime using green light outperforms the contact regime with red light. Firstly, we noted that the low sampling frequency significantly limits the maximum theoretical resolution. At 95 Hz, a 10.5 ms error is already introduced, putting a significantly high lower bound on the minimum jitter that can be achieved. Nonetheless, in the contact regime with red light, satisfactory results were achieved with a jitter of 12.6 ms across all patients computed from the onset point of the PPG waveform (PAT_O). The PAT aligns with the ranges reported in the literature, with PAT_f in the range 80 ms to 120 ms. Based on the measurement of subject 2, it is estimated that increasing the sampling frequency up to 235 Hz in this regime can yield a decrease of the jitter by an additional 31-42%. Increasing the sampling rate improves temporal resolution and can reduce quantization error in timing-related measurements; however, these benefits are expected to progressively saturate once the acquisition rate approaches the relevant physiological signal bandwidth and the timing precision required by the target application. Beyond this point, further increases mainly result in higher data throughput, processing load, and storage requirements, with limited practical performance improvements. Therefore, the sampling rate used in this work was selected as a pragmatic trade-off between temporal fidelity and implementation complexity, and substantially higher rates are not expected to provide proportionate benefit in the present setting. The foot and onset points are both auspicious, with acceptance rates of 99.4% and 99.0%, respectively. Additionally, the arrival time of these two fiducial points is 100 ms and 180 ms in comparison to the R-peak. On the other hand, the systolic peak is poorly detected due to the reflective red PPG's morphology. Commonly, the diastolic peak has an amplitude close to or exceeding the systolic peak, leading to its detection as the local maximum. As a result, it can be observed that a significant percentage of the systolic points are rejected and do not fall within the expected acceptance region, as shown in Table 5 and Table 7. Therefore, it is strongly discouraged to use the systolic peak as the reference point for MRI triggering.

The contactless green PPG measurements at 235 Hz performed better than the red PPG in contact. The reported jitters in Table 4 are 5.14 ms and 5.13 ms for both the foot and onset fiducial points, while maintaining similar PATs compared to the contact measurement. Both points are extremely reliable in this regime, with a detection rate of 100% and 99.9%. The variability of the jitter based on the systolic peak point is again large due to the different morphology of the PPG waveform in each subject. For example for subject 5 $Jitter_p$ is 6.64 ms with an acceptance rate of 98.6%, while for subject one the $Jitter_p$ is 30.5 ms with only 59.3% acceptance rate. The large PAT_p and its inconsistency across patients make triggering using the systolic peak unfeasible in clinical applications.

In our young, healthy cohort (mean age 25 ± 4 years), PAT and jitter were consistently low, reflecting high vascular compliance and minimal autonomic or blood pressure-related variability. In older populations, increased arterial stiffness accelerates pulse wave velocity [7], shortening PAT and potentially affecting jitter. Blood pressure, whether chronically elevated or fluctuating due to autonomic regulation, further affects arterial compliance and pulse wave timing, potentially affecting jitter. These factors suggest that while foot and onset points are robust for MRI triggering in young adults,

Figure 9: With reference to Figure 5, this plot shows the error distribution between the real peak and the predicted (prospective) peak onboard the sensor node. The test is conducted under controlled conditions (Evaluation) and during an MRI scan (MRI) on the same subject. The error follows a Gaussian distribution with $\mu = 0.6$ ms, $\sigma = 13$ ms and $\mu = 17$ ms, $\sigma = 181$ ms for Evaluation and MRI, respectively.

careful evaluation is needed in older or hypertensive subjects to maintain low-latency, low-jitter performance.

5.2 Sensor Node Power Profile

To ensure the device can operate throughout a typical MRI scan without recharging, its current consumption is analyzed. After initialization, it reaches normal operation approximately 1.6 s later. The average current consumption, measured over ≈ 2 h, is 10.49 mA. To estimate the battery lifetime during normal operations, an endurance test is performed using the same setup described in Section 3.3, with the red LED on. During the test, fuel gauge and PPG data are continuously transmitted over BLE and logged to a text file (see Section 4.2) to emulate a real measurement campaign. To estimate the device's endurance, we assume the LEDs are powered by 3.6 V, thereby setting a lower bound on the battery discharge. Based on the endurance test, a linear approximation is used to estimate the battery time, resulting in a voltage slope defined as $V_{slope} = \frac{\Delta \text{voltage}}{\Delta \text{time}} \approx 0.352 \text{ mV min}^{-1}$. In other words, the battery of 520 mA h lasts 23 h and 40 min during continuous PPG sampling and logging, a value that is much longer than a typical MRI scan; usually, MRI takes between 20 min to 60 min [8]. Therefore, if the battery is initially fully charged, it powers the sensor node between 23 and 70 MRI scans, more than enough to cover one working day.

6 MRI Deployment and Measurements

To evaluate the performance of the PPG device within the MRI environment, experiments were conducted on a Philips MRI system (Philips Healthcare, Best, the Netherlands) at multiple field strengths (0.6, 1.5, and 3 Tesla). All volunteers provided written informed consent in accordance with institutional and ethical guidelines. Participants were positioned inside the scanner bore following a standard cardiac MRI protocol, with a cardiac coil placed over the torso and the PPG device mounted on the forehead, as shown in the center and right detail of Figure 1.

Figure 10: CINE images at 0.6 T of different cardiac planes for one subject: four-chamber, three-chamber, and two-chamber views. The top row shows images acquired without the PPG device, and the bottom row shows images acquired with it. Colored patches indicate the regions used for SNR measurements: green for the LV, blue for the RV, and yellow for the LA.

Table 8: SNR for the different regions and cardiac views highlighted in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

SNR		0.6T		3T	
Cardiac View	Region	No PPG	PPG	No PPG	PPG
4 Chamber	RV	29.6	26.8	497.5	476.2
	LV	33.3	26.8	247.4	242.1
	RA	35.9	28.9	448.3	508.5
3 Chamber	RV	26.4	22.8	415.0	510.4
2 Chamber	RV	24.9	23.7	369.1	354.2

CINE images were acquired at 0.6 T and 3 T in one subject per field strength to assess image quality and potential artifacts introduced by the PPG device. Imaging was performed using balanced fast field echo (B-FFE) sequences across three standard cardiac planes: four-chamber, three-chamber, and two-chamber views. Datasets were collected both with and without PPG, with all acquisitions synchronized using the ECG (Invivo/Philips). Image quality was evaluated by measuring the SNR [11] in the right ventricle (RV), left ventricle (LV), and right atrium (RA). Side-by-side comparisons (Figure 10 and Figure 11) indicate that the presence of the PPG device did not introduce artifacts or distortions. SNR values (Table 8) were comparable with and without the device across cardiac regions and views. These results are based on a single subject, and further studies in a larger cohort are required to generalize the findings.

To evaluate the performance of the PPG signal under MRI conditions, volunteers underwent various flow MRI acquisitions, including 2D breath-hold and 4D flow sequences, all triggered by the ECG using the Invivo/Philips system as the ground truth. The PPG signal was acquired either in contact mode or in contactless mode,

Figure 11: CINE images at 3 T of different cardiac planes for one subject: four-chamber, three-chamber, and two-chamber views. The top row shows images acquired without the PPG device, and the bottom row shows images acquired with it. Colored patches indicate the regions used for SNR measurements: green for the LV, blue for the RV, and yellow for the LA.

as shown in Figure 6. Four surface electrodes were placed on the torso for cardiac gating, while PPG signals were simultaneously recorded from the forehead. Throughout the experiments, no BLE disconnections or significant packet loss were observed, demonstrating the robustness of the sensor node and wireless BLE link against electromagnetic interference. Additionally, no artifacts or interference attributable to the PPG electronics were detected in the MR images, confirming the effectiveness of the non-ferromagnetic fiber bundle design described in Section 3.2.

The analysis of the red and green PPG signals demonstrates that the relative magnitude of the fundamental frequency in the interest spectrum remains. In the low-frequency range (0.1 Hz to 0.5 Hz), both signals exhibit motion-related artifacts; however, their amplitudes are comparatively smaller than those of the cardiac frequency components. Conversely, the red PPG signal shows a higher level of high-frequency noise. The Chebyshev Type II band-pass filter effectively mitigates both motion and high-frequency artifacts while preserving the fundamental cardiac frequencies. Quantitative results for both measurement regimes are summarized in Table 9. The computed SNR, S_{SQI} , peak amplitude, and zero-crossing signal quality index (Z_{SQI}) indicate consistently high-quality PPG signals. Both green and red PPG achieved SNR values above 20 dB, with green PPG exhibiting an approximately 2 dB higher SNR. Although the fundamental frequency peak of green PPG is smaller in absolute magnitude, its noise floor is lower, resulting in an improved SNR. The red PPG signal, in contrast, shows roughly twice the peak amplitude and an S_{SQI} of 0.56, corresponding to an acceptable to near-excellent signal quality as reported in prior studies [5]. The Z_{SQI} values are notably low for both signals, confirming high periodicity and minimal noise contamination in each case.

Processing the PPG timeseries onboard is also possible during MRI scans, with a visible heart signal and visually identifiable fiducial points; however, as discussed above, we observed a considerable

Table 9: Quantitative analysis of PPG regimes under MRI conditions. Contact values are acquired using the red LED, while non-contact values are acquired using the green LED. For SNR and amplitude, higher values are better; for the remaining metrics, lower values are better.

Regime	SNR (dB)	S _{SQI}	Amplitude	Z _{SQI}
Contact	20	0.56	730	0.0163
Non-contact	22	0.35	313	0.0042

number of artifacts and increased noise, resulting in several spectral components in the frequency domain. Even without completely corrupting the PPG signal, real-time peak detection and prediction become non-trivial. Indeed, one of the main limitations found during the MRI deployment is the limited accuracy of the peak detector used for prospective MRI triggering. As visible in Figure 9, the MRI error distribution is not longer centered around the 13 ms standard deviation of the Evaluation characterization, but it increases to $\sigma = 181$ and a mean of 17 ms. Values not acceptable for prospective analysis, that needs to be below 25 ms [4, 9, 33, 36]. Therefore, an algorithm finetuning is required to increase the robustness and consistency of the real-time prospective gating.

7 Limitations and Future Work

Although this study demonstrates the feasibility of an MRI-compatible PPG system, several limitations should be noted. The initial pilot evaluation was conducted outside the MRI environment on a small cohort of young healthy volunteers, limiting the assessment of performance under physiological and usage variability. In this same pilot setting, certain acquisition modes and device configurations were explored only in preliminary form, and some observed differences, such as contactless green outperforming contact red, are specific to the controlled operating regime and may not generalize to broader use conditions. In contrast, the MRI feasibility experiments were performed at a single site under controlled scanning conditions and, for each acquisition mode or device configuration, were evaluated on a single subject. This further restricts the ability to assess inter-subject variability and limits the generalizability of the results across populations, MRI vendors, field strengths, and acquisition protocols. The current findings should therefore be interpreted as indicative of technical feasibility rather than representative of comprehensive cross-site or cross-population performance. Future work will focus on expanding the subject cohort to better capture variability between users and conditions, validating performance across additional field strengths, scanners, and MRI protocols, and exploring algorithmic improvements such as adaptive thresholds, calibration routines, and confidence-aware peak detection.

While the system was evaluated against previously reported camera-based PPG results in terms of trigger delay and jitter, a synchronized, side-by-side comparison was not performed. Such a direct evaluation would provide a stronger basis for quantitative performance assessment, particularly with respect to absolute latency and temporal stability under identical physiological and environmental conditions. The absence of a simultaneous camera

baseline was primarily due to time and resource constraints, as the primary objective of this work was to validate MRI-compatible operation and to characterize the proposed fiber-optic system. Future work should therefore include a controlled, synchronized comparison to enable comprehensive benchmarking of delay, jitter, and gating robustness against camera-based approaches.

In the intended MRI use scenario, sensor distance and angle can be selected and fixed during setup, and this study demonstrates feasibility under the specific configuration adopted here. A systematic characterization across varying distances and angular alignments was outside the scope of the present work and will be addressed in future studies. Additionally, as future work, extending the system to additional wavelengths may be valuable, as multi-wavelength sensing could provide complementary sensitivity to tissue composition and hemodynamics, potentially improving robustness and measurement quality across subjects and acquisition conditions.

8 Conclusion

This work presents a feasibility study for an MRI-compatible, fiber-optic PPG system designed for safe and reliable cardiac monitoring and prospective gating. The proposed approach combines optical isolation, embedded real-time processing, and wireless data transmission to address limitations of traditional ECG-based gating inside MRI scanners. By routing light through custom-manufactured, non-ferromagnetic fiber bundles, the system ensures immunity to electromagnetic interference while maintaining patient comfort through a contactless measurement configuration.

The developed sensor node, powered by a low-power nRF5340 SoC and an ADPD4100 optical front-end, features efficient onboard processing with a total computational latency of only 2.8 ms and continuous operation for over 23 h on a single charge. The non-contact green-light configuration achieved a pulse arrival jitter of 5 ms, surpassing state-of-the-art camera-based approaches. In-bore testing further confirmed the absence of RF interference and demonstrated consistent cardiac signal detection suitable for MRI gating. Overall, this work establishes fiber-optic contactless PPG as a viable and safe alternative to ECG for MRI cardiac synchronization. The combination of optical isolation, high timing precision, and low-power embedded design paves the way for next-generation multimodal MRI-compatible physiological monitoring systems supporting robust and interference-free imaging workflows.

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